

Versioned Archive and Review of Biotic
Interactions and Taxon Names Found within
globalbioticinteractions/web-of-life
hash://md5/3a3ef5d6fb5aa1e008174496e4216f47

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Abstract

Life on Earth is sustained by complex interactions between organisms and their environment. These biotic interactions can be captured in datasets and published digitally. We present a review and archiving process for such an openly accessible digital interactions dataset of known origin and discuss its outcome. The dataset under review, named `globalbioticinteractions/web-of-life`, has fingerprint hash://md5/3a3ef5d6fb5aa1e008174496e4216f47, is 300KiB in size and contains 72,201 interactions with 6 unique types of associations (e.g., `pollinatedBy`) between 5,328 primary taxa (e.g., `Detritus`) and 11,029 associated taxa (e.g., `Apis mellifera`). This report includes detailed summaries of interaction data, a taxonomic review from multiple catalogs, and an archived version of the dataset from which the reviews are derived.

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Introduction

Data Review and Archive

Data review and archiving can be a time-consuming process, especially when done manually. This review report aims to help facilitate both activities. It automates the archiving of datasets, including Darwin Core archives, and is a citable backup of a version of the dataset. Additionally, an automatic review of species interaction claims made in the dataset is generated and registered with Global Biotic Interactions (J. H. Poelen, Simons, and Mungall 2014).

This review includes summary statistics about, and observations about, the dataset under review :

Web of Life. <http://www.web-of-life.es> . <https://github.com/globalbioticinteractions/web-of-life/archive/f63e4dbd52d31b698df5d5f63a409889a26fd0a5.zip>
2026-06-02T22:48:09.819Z hash://md5/3a3ef5d6fb5aa1e008174496e4216f47

Methods

The review is performed through programmatic scripts that leverage tools like Preston (Elliott et al. 2025), Elton (Kuhn, Poelen, and Leinweber 2025), Nomer (Salim and Poelen 2025), globinizer (J. Poelen, Seltmann, and Mietchen 2024) combined with third-party tools like grep, mlr, tail and head.

Table 1: Tools used in this review process

tool name	version
preston	0.11.1
elton	0.16.11

tool name	version
nomer	0.6.5
globinizer	0.4.0
mlr	6.0.0
jq	1.6
yq	4.25.3
pandoc	3.1.6.1
duckdb	1.3.1
mapserver	7.6.4

The review process can be described in the form of the script below ¹.

```
# get versioned copy of the dataset (size approx. 300KiB) under review
elton pull globalbioticinteractions/web-of-life

# generate review notes
elton review globalbioticinteractions/web-of-life \
  > review.tsv

# export indexed interaction records
elton interactions globalbioticinteractions/web-of-life \
  > interactions.tsv

# export names and align them with the Catalogue of Life using Nomer
elton names globalbioticinteractions/web-of-life \
  | nomer append col \
  > name-alignment.tsv
```

or visually, in a process diagram.

Figure 1: Review Process Overview

You can find a copy of the full review script at [check-data.sh](#). See also [GitHub](#) and [Codeberg](#).

¹Note that you have to first get the data (e.g., via `elton pull globalbioticinteractions/web-of-life`) before being able to generate reviews (e.g., `elton review globalbioticinteractions/web-of-life`), extract interaction claims (e.g., `elton interactions globalbioticinteractions/web-of-life`), or list taxonomic names (e.g., `elton names globalbioticinteractions/web-of-life`)

Results

In the following sections, the results of the review are summarized ². Then, links to the detailed review reports are provided.

Files

An extensive list of files produced as part of the review process can be found in Appendix A. Review Files.

Archived Dataset

Note that *data.zip* file in this archive contains the complete, unmodified archived dataset under review.

Biotic Interactions

Figure 2: Biotic Interaction Data Model

In this review, biotic interactions (or biotic associations) are modeled as a primary (aka subject, source) organism interacting with an associate (aka object, target) organism. The dataset under review classified the primary/associate organisms with specific taxa. The primary and associate organisms The kind of interaction is documented as an interaction type.

The dataset under review, named `globalbioticinteractions/web-of-life`, has fingerprint hash://md5/3a3ef5d6fb5aa1e008174496e4216f47, is 300KiB in size and contains 72,201 interactions with 6 unique types of associations (e.g., `pollinatedBy`) between 5,328 primary taxa (e.g., `Detritus`) and 11,029 associated taxa (e.g., `Apis mellifera`).

An exhaustive list of indexed interaction claims can be found in gzipped `csv`, `tsv`, `geopackage` and `parquet` archives. To facilitate discovery, a preview of claims available in the gzipped `html` page at `indexed-interactions.html.gz` are shown below.

The exhaustive list was used to create the following data summaries below.

²Disclaimer: The results in this review should be considered friendly, yet naive, notes from an unsophisticated robot. Please keep that in mind when considering the review results.

Table 2: Sample of Indexed Interaction Claims

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeName	targetTaxonName	referenceCitation
Apodemus mystacinus	hasParasite	Num. of hosts sampled	Hadfield JD, Krasnov BR, Poulin R, Shinichi N (2013) A tale of two phylogenies: comparative analyses of ecological interactions. The American Naturalist 183(2): 174-187
Apodemus mystacinus	hasParasite	Ctenophthalmus euxinicus	Hadfield JD, Krasnov BR, Poulin R, Shinichi N (2013) A tale of two phylogenies: comparative analyses of ecological interactions. The American Naturalist 183(2): 174-187
Apodemus mystacinus	hasParasite	Ctenophthalmus hypanis	Hadfield JD, Krasnov BR, Poulin R, Shinichi N (2013) A tale of two phylogenies: comparative analyses of ecological interactions. The American Naturalist 183(2): 174-187

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeName	targetTaxonName	referenceCitation
Apodemus mystacinus	hasParasite	Ctenophthalmus proximus	Hadfield JD, Krasnov BR, Poulin R, Shinichi N (2013) A tale of two phylogenies: comparative analyses of ecological interactions. The American Naturalist 183(2): 174-187

Table 3: Most Frequently Mentioned Interaction Types (up to 20 most frequent)

interactionTypeName	count
pollinatedBy	44510
eatenBy	17181
hasDispersalVector	5247
hasParasite	4608
interactsWith	477
hostOf	178

Table 4: Most Frequently Mentioned Primary Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

sourceTaxonName	count
Detritus	655
Zooplankton	539
Decapoda sp1 FW_017	526
Actinopterygii	388
Worm	362
Benthic autotroph	326
Gastropoda	305
Eryngium stenophyllum	305
Nephrosperma vanhoutteanum	297
Microtus arvalis	247
Clethrionomys rutilus	234

sourceTaxonName	count
Fragilaria vaucheriae	223
Apodemus uralensis	220
Clethrionomys glareolus	212
Cymbella minuta	202
Synedra ulna	200
Diatoma heimale	198
Rhoicosphenia curvata	198
Persicaria thunbergii	198

Table 5: Most Frequently Mentioned Associate Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

targetTaxonName	count
Apis mellifera	892
Num. of hosts sampled	624
Aphrophila noevaezelandiae	235
Lasioglossum mahense	224
Carcharhinus perezii	196
Salmo trutta	192
Oligochaeta type II	188
Augochlora semiramis	182
Austrosimulium australense	179
Episyrphus balteatus	179
Galeocерdo cuvieri	170
Amalaraeus penicilliger	164
Ctenophthalmus assimilis	159
Spallanzania hesperidarum	157
Thalurania glaucopsis	156
Carcharhinus falciformis	155
Oscinis coxendix	151
Potamopyrgus antipodarum	147
Coloburiscus humeralis	138

Table 6: Most Frequent Interactions between Primary and Associate Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeName	targetTaxonName	count
Nephrosperma vanhoutteanum	pollinatedBy	Apis mellifera	38

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeName	targetTaxonName	count
Nephrosperma vanhoutteanum	pollinatedBy	Lasioglossum mahense	36
Erythroxyllum sechellarum	pollinatedBy	Lasioglossum mahense	32
Memecylon eleagni	pollinatedBy	Apis mellifera	31
Erythroxyllum sechellarum	pollinatedBy	Apis mellifera	26
Memecylon eleagni	pollinatedBy	Lasioglossum mahense	25
Microtus arvalis	hasParasite	Num. of hosts sampled	23
Apodemus uralensis	hasParasite	Num. of hosts sampled	23
Dillenia ferruginea	pollinatedBy	Apis mellifera	22
Arvicola terrestris	hasParasite	Num. of hosts sampled	21
Microtus oeconomus	hasParasite	Num. of hosts sampled	21
Sorex araneus	hasParasite	Num. of hosts sampled	20
Phoenicophorium borsigianum	pollinatedBy	Lasioglossum mahense	20
Cricetulus migratorius	hasParasite	Num. of hosts sampled	19
Clethrionomys rutilus	hasParasite	Num. of hosts sampled	19
Paragenipa wrightii	pollinatedBy	Apis mellifera	19
Paragenipa wrightii	pollinatedBy	Lasioglossum mahense	19
Nephrosperma vanhoutteanum	pollinatedBy	Neophyllomyza approximaton- ervis	19
Clethrionomys glareolus	hasParasite	Num. of hosts sampled	18

Interaction Networks

The figures below provide a graph view on the dataset under review. The first shows a summary network on the kingdom level, and the second shows how interactions on the family level. It is important to note that both network graphs were first aligned taxonomically using the Catalogue of Life. Please refer

to the original (or verbatim) taxonomic names for a more original view on the interaction data.

Figure 3: Interactions on taxonomic kingdom rank as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life download `svg`

You can download the indexed dataset under review at `indexed-interactions.csv.gz`. A tab-separated file can be found at `indexed-interactions.tsv.gz`

Geospatial Distribution

If geospatial information was extracted from the dataset under review, the map below will show their distribution. These maps were generated using MapServer (McKenna et al. 2025) tools configured via map configuration `indexed-interactions.map` :

Figure 4: Interactions on the taxonomic family rank as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life. [download svg](#)

MAP

```

SIZE 1600 800
EXTENT -180 -90 180 90
PROJECTION
  "init=epsg:4326"
END
LAYER # MODIS WMS map from NASA
  NAME      "modis_nasa"
  TYPE      RASTER
  OFFSITE   0 0 0
  STATUS    ON
  CONNECTIONTYPE WMS
  CONNECTION "https://gibs.earthdata.nasa.gov/wms/epsg4326/best/wms.cgi?"

```

METADATA

```

"wms_srs" "EPSG:4326"
"wms_name" "OSM_Land_Water_Map"
"wms_server_version" "1.1.1"
"wms_format" "image/jpeg"
END
CLASS
  STYLE
    COLOR      232 232 232

```

```

        OUTLINECOLOR 32 32 32
      END
    END
  END
LAYER
  NAME "indexed-interactions"
  TYPE POLYGON
  STATUS ON
  CONNECTIONTYPE OGR
  CONNECTION "indexed-interactions-h3.gpkg"
  DATA "indexed-interactions-h3"
  CLASS
    STYLE
      COLORRANGE 253.0 231.0 37.0 32.0 164.0 134.0
      DATARANGE 1.0791812460476249 4.1834406800379496
      RANGEITEM "log_number_of_records"
      OUTLINECOLOR 0 0 0
    END
  END
END
END
END

```


Figure 5: Hexagonal grid cells indicate that interactions claims are available for selected geospatial area: light yellow means relatively fewer claims, dark green relatively more claims.

Associated data can be found in the geopackage files at `indexed-interactions.gpkg` for point data and `indexed-interactions-h3.gpkg` for data clustered in geospatial h3 hexagonals.

Learn more about the structure of this download at GloBI website, by opening

a GitHub issue, or by sending an email.

Another way to discover the dataset under review is by searching for it on the GloBI website.

Taxonomic Alignment

As part of the review, all names are aligned against various name catalogs (e.g., col, ncbi, discoverlife, gbif, itis, wfo, mdd, tpt, pbdb, and worms). These alignments can help review name usage or aid in selecting of a suitable taxonomic name resource.

Table 7: Sample of Name Alignments

providedName	relationName	resolvedCatalogName	resolvedName
Abalistes stellaris	SYNONYM_OF	col	Abalistes stellatus
Abarema brachystachya	SYNONYM_OF	col	Jupunba brachystachya
Abarema jupunba	SYNONYM_OF	col	Jupunba trapezifolia var. micradenia
Abeillia abeillei	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	col	Abeillia abeillei

Table 8: Distribution of Taxonomic Ranks of Aligned Names by Catalog. Names that were not aligned with a catalog are counted as NAs. So, the total number of unaligned names for a catalog will be listed in their NA row.

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
col	NA	2042
col	class	20
col	domain	1
col	family	84
col	genus	899
col	gigaclass	1
col	infraclass	1
col	infraorder	1
col	kingdom	2
col	order	20
col	phylum	6
col	species	8315
col	subclass	1
col	subfamily	10

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
col	subgenus	30
col	suborder	4
col	subphylum	1
col	subspecies	258
col	subtribe	2
col	superfamily	5
col	tribe	17
col	variety	51
discoverlife	NA	10694
discoverlife	species	873
gbif	NA	2074
gbif	class	21
gbif	family	87
gbif	form	4
gbif	genus	909
gbif	kingdom	3
gbif	order	20
gbif	phylum	5
gbif	species	8293
gbif	subspecies	295
gbif	variety	74
itis	NA	5838
itis	class	18
itis	division	1
itis	family	80
itis	genus	665
itis	infraorder	1
itis	kingdom	3
itis	order	21
itis	phylum	5
itis	species	4809
itis	subclass	6
itis	subfamily	11
itis	subgenus	3
itis	suborder	4
itis	subphylum	3
itis	subspecies	53
itis	superclass	1
itis	superdivision	1
itis	superfamily	5
itis	tribe	5
itis	variety	43
mdd	NA	11566
ncbi	NA	4298

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
nbi	clade	3
nbi	class	19
nbi	family	82
nbi	genus	816
nbi	infraorder	1
nbi	kingdom	1
nbi	order	21
nbi	parvorder	1
nbi	phylum	9
nbi	species	6232
nbi	subclass	3
nbi	subfamily	16
nbi	subgenus	37
nbi	suborder	2
nbi	subphylum	1
nbi	subspecies	35
nbi	superclass	1
nbi	superfamily	5
nbi	superkingdom	1
nbi	tribe	3
nbi	varietas	13
pdb	NA	10715
pdb	class	23
pdb	family	84
pdb	genus	417
pdb	informal	1
pdb	infraclass	1
pdb	infraorder	1
pdb	kingdom	2
pdb	order	22
pdb	phylum	6
pdb	species	265
pdb	subclass	4
pdb	subfamily	14
pdb	subkingdom	1
pdb	suborder	4
pdb	subphylum	1
pdb	superclass	1
pdb	superfamily	5
pdb	tribe	4
pdb	unranked clade	7
tpt	NA	10703
tpt	genus	9
tpt	species	854

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
tpt	subspecific epithet	1
wfo	NA	8054
wfo	family	14
wfo	genus	239
wfo	species	3218
wfo	subspecies	51
wfo	variety	34
worms	NA	9506
worms	class	17
worms	family	67
worms	forma	3
worms	genus	344
worms	gigaclass	1
worms	infraclass	1
worms	infraorder	1
worms	kingdom	3
worms	order	20
worms	phylum	6
worms	phylum (division)	2
worms	species	1575
worms	subclass	4
worms	subfamily	2
worms	suborder	2
worms	subphylum	3
worms	subspecies	13
worms	superfamily	3
worms	tribe	2
worms	variety	16

Table 9: Name relationship types per catalog. Name relationship type “NONE” means that a name was not recognized by the associated catalog. “SAME_AS” indicates either a “HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME” or “SYNONYM_OF” name relationship type. We recognize that “SYNONYM_OF” encompasses many types of nomenclatural synonymies (ICZN 1999) (e.g., junior synonym, senior synonyms).

resolvedCatalogName	relationName	count
col	SYNONYM_OF	4516
col	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	10075
col	NONE	4324
discoverlife	NONE	14806

resolvedCatalogName	relationName	count
discoverlife	SYNONYM_OF	436
discoverlife	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	612
discoverlife	HOMONYM_OF	54
gbif	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	11302
gbif	SYNONYM_OF	4948
gbif	NONE	4385
itis	SYNONYM_OF	1112
itis	NONE	8326
itis	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	6483
mdd	NONE	15546
mdd	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	125
mdd	SYNONYM_OF	3
ncbi	SAME_AS	8663
ncbi	SYNONYM_OF	693
ncbi	NONE	6605
ncbi	COMMON_NAME_OF	1
pbdb	NONE	13505
pbdb	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	2204
pbdb	SYNONYM_OF	137
tpt	NONE	14798
tpt	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	1038
tpt	SYNONYM_OF	97
wfo	NONE	11826
wfo	SYNONYM_OF	1292
wfo	HAS_UNCHECKED_NAME	362
wfo	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	2996
worms	SYNONYM_OF	450
worms	NONE	12609
worms	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	3063

Table 10: List of Available Name Alignment Reports

catalog name	alignment results
col	associated names alignments report in zipped html, csv, and tsv)
ncbi	associated names alignments report in zipped html, csv, and tsv)
discoverlife	associated names alignments report in zipped html, csv, and tsv)
gbif	associated names alignments report in zipped html, csv, and tsv)

catalog name	alignment results
itis	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
wfo	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
mdd	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
tpt	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
pbdb	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
worms	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)

Additional Reviews

Elton, Nomer, and other tools may have difficulties interpreting existing species interaction datasets. Or, they may misbehave, or otherwise show unexpected behavior. As part of the review process, detailed review notes are kept that document possibly misbehaving, or confused, review bots. An sample of review notes associated with this review can be found below.

Table 11: First few lines in the review notes.

reviewDate	reviewCommentType	reviewComment
2026-06-04T05:35:38Z	summary	https://github.com/globalbioticinteractions/web-of-life/archive/f63e4dbd52d31b698df5d5f63a409889a26fd0a
2026-06-04T05:35:38Z	summary	72201 interaction(s)
2026-06-04T05:35:38Z	summary	0 note(s)
2026-06-04T05:35:38Z	summary	0 info(s)

In addition, you can find the most frequently occurring notes in the table below.

: Most frequently occurring review notes, if any.

For additional information on review notes, please have a look at the first 500 Review Notes in html format or the download full gzipped csv or tsv archives.

GloBI Review Badge

As part of the review, a review badge is generated. This review badge can be included in webpages to indicate the review status of the dataset under review.

³Up-to-date status of the GloBI Review Badge can be retrieved from the GloBI Review Depot

Figure 6: Picture of a GloBI Review Badge ³

Note that if the badge is green, no review notes were generated. If the badge is yellow, the review bots may need some help with interpreting the species interaction data.

GloBI Index Badge

If the dataset under review has been registered with GloBI, and has been successfully indexed by GloBI, the GloBI Index Status Badge will turn green. This means that the dataset under review was indexed by GloBI and is available through GloBI services and derived data products.

Figure 7: Picture of a GloBI Index Badge ⁴

If you'd like to keep track of reviews or index status of the dataset under review, please visit GloBI's dataset index ⁵ for badge examples.

Discussion

This review and archive provides a means of creating citable versions of datasets that change frequently. This may be useful for dataset managers, including natural history collection data managers, as a backup archive of a shared Darwin Core archive. It also serves as a means of creating a trackable citation for the dataset in an automated way, while also including some information about the contents of the dataset.

This review aims to provide a perspective on the dataset to aid in understanding of species interaction claims discovered. However, it is important to note that this review does *not* assess the quality of the dataset. Instead, it serves as an indication of the open-ness⁶ and FAIRness (Wilkinson et al. 2016; Trekels et al. 2023) of the dataset: to perform this review, the data was likely openly available, **F**indable, **A**ccessible, **I**nteroperable and **R**eusable. The current Open-FAIR assessment is qualitative, and a more quantitative approach can be implemented with specified measurement units.

⁴Up-to-date status of the GloBI Index Badge can be retrieved from GloBI's API

⁵At time of writing (2026-06-04) the version of the GloBI dataset index was available at <https://globalbioticinteractions.org/datasets>

⁶According to <http://opendefinition.org/>: "Open data is data that can be freely used, re-used and redistributed by anyone - subject only, at most, to the requirement to attribute and sharealike."

This report also showcases the reuse of machine-actionable (meta)data, something highly recommended by the FAIR Data Principles (Wilkinson et al. 2016). Making (meta)data machine-actionable enables more precise processing by computers, enabling even naive review bots like Nomer and Elton to interpret the data effectively. This capability is crucial for not just automating the generation of reports, but also for facilitating seamless data exchanges, promoting interoperability.

Acknowledgements

We thank the many humans that created us and those who created and maintained the data, software and other intellectual resources that were used for producing this review. In addition, we are grateful for the natural resources providing the basis for these human and bot activities. Also, thanks to <https://github.com/zygoballus> for helping improve the layout of the review tables.

Author contributions

Nomer was responsible for name alignments. Elton carried out dataset extraction, and generated the review notes. Preston tracked, versioned, and packaged, the dataset under review.

Appendix A. Review Files

The following files are produced in this review:

filename	description
biblio.bib	list of bibliographic reference of this review
check-dataset.sh	data review workflow/process as expressed in a bash script
data.zip	a versioned archive of the data under review
HEAD	the digital signature of the data under review
index.docx	review in MS Word format
index.html	review in HTML format
index.md	review in Pandoc markdown format
index.pdf	review in PDF format

filename	description
indexed-citations.csv.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interaction claims in gzipped comma-separated values file format
indexed-citations.html.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interactions claims in gzipped html file format
indexed-citations.tsv.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interaction claims in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-interactions-col-family-col-family.svg	network diagram showing the taxon family to taxon family interaction claims in the dataset under review as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life via Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024)
indexed-interactions-col-kingdom-col-kingdom.svg	network diagram showing the taxon kingdom to taxon kingdom interaction claims in the dataset under review as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life via Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024)
indexed-interactions.csv.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-interactions.html.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped html format
indexed-interactions.tsv.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-interactions.parquet	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in Apache Parquet format
indexed-interactions.png	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review plotted on a map
indexed-interactions.map	mapserver configuration to plot species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review on a map

filename	description
indexed-interactions.gpkg	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in GeoPackage format
indexed-interactions-h3.gpkg	geospatially clustered h3 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in GeoPackage format
indexed-interactions-sample.csv	list of species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-interactions-sample.html	first 500 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in html format
indexed-interactions-sample.tsv	first 500 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
indexed-names.csv.gz	taxonomic names indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in gzipped html format
indexed-names.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-col.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-col.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-col.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-col.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-itis.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-worms.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-sample.csv	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in comma-separated values format
indexed-names-sample.html	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in html format
indexed-names-sample.tsv	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
interaction.svg	diagram summarizing the data model used to index species interaction claims
nanopub-sample.trig	first 500 species interaction claims as expressed in the nanopub format (Kuhn and Dumontier 2014)
nanopub.trig.gz	species interaction claims as expressed in the nanopub format (Kuhn and Dumontier 2014)
process.svg	diagram summarizing the data review processing workflow
prov.nq	origin of the dataset under review as expressed in rdf/nquads

filename	description
review.csv.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
review.html.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped html format
review.tsv.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
review-sample.csv	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in comma-separated values format
review-sample.html	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in html format
review-sample.tsv	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
review.svg	a review badge generated as part of the dataset review process
zenodo.json	metadata of this review expressed in Zenodo record metadata

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